

Portfolio selection based on predictive approach

Sélection de portefeuille basée sur une approche prédictive

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Abstract

The paper analyzes a conceptual value investor behavior that uses stock fundamentals to predict the best-performing portfolio according to the knowledge it has at its disposal from previous periods. A class of machine learning algorithms based on inductive learning is used to learn from past data and predict by induced rules which stock to select for the final portfolio. This approach has led not only to corroborate with other research on the relevance of financial fundamentals to explain the future returns of stock but also to design a strategy that generates significant excess returns compared to the market index, S&P 500.

Keywords.

Portfolio Choice, Investment Decisions, Asset Management, Machine Learning, Decision Tree, Value Investing.

Résumé

L'article analyse le comportement conceptuel d'un investisseur dans la valeur qui utilise les fondamentaux des sociétés cotées pour prédire le portefeuille le plus performant en fonction des connaissances dont il dispose sur les périodes précédentes. Pour se faire, une classe d'algorithmes d'apprentissage automatique basée sur l'apprentissage inductif est utilisée pour apprendre des données passées et prédire par des règles induites quels actions sélectionnés pour construire le portefeuille final. Cette approche a conduit non seulement à corroborer avec d'autres recherches sur la pertinence des fondamentaux financiers à expliquer les rendements futurs des actions mais aussi à concevoir une stratégie générant des rendements excédentaires significatifs par rapport à l'indice du marché considéré, le S&P 500.

Mots clés

Sélection de Portefeuille, Décisions d'investissement, Gestion d'actif, Machine Learning, Arbre de Décision, Investissement dans la Valeur

1. Introduction

The portfolio selection problem concerns which stocks to select and how to allocate limited capital between them in order to maximize a utility function with respect to stock market investment. Many are theories, models, and approaches that had been proposed through the literature of finance to answer this problem. Even if, more than half a century after its appearance, the Modern Theory of Portfolio (Markowitz, 1952) seems to be accepted, several investors do not apply it in practice. Still, they privilege the traditional approach of fundamental analysis. Indeed, going back even further, a book titled *Security Analysis* (Graham & Dodd, 1934) is known as a treatise on analyzing stocks. Many are the defenders of this approach of whom the most famous is Warren Buffet¹ also known as the Oracle of Omaha, who needs no introduction. This book, echoing the lessons learned from the then-recent crisis of 1929, has remained a foundational reference for the value investing. *Value investing* is an investment paradigm that uses fundamental analysis to identify and invest in stocks that trade at a discount to their intrinsic or fair value.

Furthermore, another masterpiece work entitled *The Intelligent Investor* (Graham, 1949), provides a precise definition of how to invest. Graham started by clarifying and defining an investor as opposed to speculator by stating what investment actually means: “*An investment operation is one which, upon thorough analysis, promises safety of principal and an adequate return. Operations not meeting these requirements are speculative*”². Graham’s definition sheds light on where the fundamental analysis must intervene in the investment process, that is in order to estimate a security’s intrinsic value by examining and analyzing deeply related financial statements, economic factors, etc. In fact, anything that can affect the stock’s fair value, from macroeconomic factors such as the state of the economy (economic level analysis) and industry conditions (industry level analysis) to microeconomic factors like the effectiveness of the company’s management (company level analysis), should be considered in the process. The main goal is to arrive at an estimation of the value that an investor can trust and use to compare with a stock’s current market price in order to see whether the stock is undervalued (in which case the investor might buy) or overvalued (otherwise sell). Additionally, the concept of safety margin as defined by Klarman (1991) is there to protect the investor against severe losses, as stated in the following: “*A margin of safety is achieved when stocks are purchased at*

¹ Warren Buffet made the work of his professor and mentor Graham, the spearhead of the investment strategy adopted by the company Berkshire Hathaway (with a Total Assets of 873.7 billion dollars in 2020) of which he is the main shareholder

² From [3, p. 18], mentioned at first time in (Graham & Dodd, Security Analysis, 1934)

prices sufficiently below underlying value to allow for human error, bad luck, or extreme volatility in a complex, unpredictable and rapidly changing world” (Klarman, 1991, p. 92(4))

The concept of risk as defined by the work of Markowitz is the moment of the second order or the variance of returns, and later more specification and precision were added to the concept of risk. For example, in the context of CAPM (Capital Asset Pricing Model), which is a One Factor Market Model (1) elaborated by Sharpe (1964), Lintner (1965) & Mossin (1966), and, there is distinction made between unsystematic risk and systematic risk. Since the latter is not controllable and depends on macroeconomic factors, diversification was therefore the watchword when it comes to portfolio design so as to mitigate the unsystematic risk which can be specific to an industry, company or stock then avoidable.

$$R_{jt} = R_{ft} + \beta_j(R_{Mt} - R_{ft}) + \epsilon_{jt}$$

Where:

- R_{jt} is the return in period t of asset j
- R_{ft} is the risk-free rate
- β_j is the sensitivity of asset j returns to the market returns R_{Mt}
- $(R_{Mt} - R_{ft})$ is the spread between the market proxy returns and risk-free rate it is also known as the market premium when it expected value's is considered.
- ϵ_{jt} is the error term

Many other models, in particular multi-factorial ones proposed and improved successively by Fama & French in (1988), (1992), (1993), and (2014) have put more emphasis on factors drawn from both market and company fundamentals, specifically in their Three Factors Market Model where size of firms, book-to market ratio (which is the ratio between the book value of equity and its market value used in particular to determine whether a stock or stock is overvalued or not) and excess return on the market are taken into account :

$$R_{jt} - R_{ft} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_{j1}(R_{Mt} - R_{ft}) + \beta_{j2}SMB_t + \beta_{j3}HML_t + \epsilon_{jt}$$

Where:

- β_{ji} is the sensitivity of asset j returns to factor i ($i \leq 3$) under consideration

Within this model, the three extracted features (2) used are SMB (Small Minus Big), HML (High Minus Low) and the portfolio's return less the risk-free rate of return where SMB

accounts for listed companies with small market capitalization that generate higher returns. HML refers to value stocks with high book-to-market ratios that generate higher returns in comparison to the market (the market index as proxy). The model has proven to explain significantly (the results of R^2 of this model applied to different sets of quantile portfolios range from 69% to 97%) the excess returns variability meaning fundamental factors cannot be ignored. Moreover, in their latest work in 2014, Fama and French adjusted their model to make it to Five Factors Market Model:

$$R_{jt} - R_{ft} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_{j1}(R_{Mt} - R_{ft}) + \beta_{j2}SMB_t + \beta_{j3}HML_t + \beta_{j3}RMW_t + \beta_{j3}CMA_t + \epsilon_{jt} \quad (3)$$

Along with the original three factors model, this new model (3) includes a fourth factor RMW: the spread between the returns on portfolios of stocks with high and low profitability, emphasizing the fact that companies achieving higher future earnings show higher returns in the stock market. That factor is referred to as profitability. The fifth factor CMA is the returns on diversified portfolios of low minus high investment stocks, referred to as investment, emphasizing the contrast between internal investment and returns, that is companies investing profit in major growth projects are more prone to under-perform in stock market. The average R^2 in the five-factor regressions range from 85% to 93%. Thus, more and more empirical research takes into account what is called "quality" and "value" which essentially includes the fundamental financial ratios. Bender, Brandhorst, & Wang (2014) in their research measured "quality" by metrics like profitability, earnings variability, and leverage; the same way "value" has been indexed by Price to Fundamental (Five fundamentals used: Earnings, Cash Flow, Sales, Dividend, and Book Value).

Other noteworthy and quite surprising research facts have been brought to light by Piotroski (2000), who designed a portfolio based on scoring stock by solely focusing on the company accounting results in recent yearly periods. The total score (F_SCORE) of each stock is the sum of signal value either 0 or 1 according to principles explained in table (Table 1).

Table 1 : Analyzing the F-SCORE

Score	Category	Definition	Signal
F_ROA	Profitability	Return On Assets (ROA)	1 IF ROA > 0 ELSE 0
F_ΔROA		Change in Return On Assets (ΔROA)	1 IF ΔROA > 0 ELSE 0
F_CFO		Cash Flow from Operations (CFO)	1 IF CFO > 0 ELSE 0
F_ACCRUAL		Accruals, measure current year's net income before extraordinary items less cash flow from operations, scaled by previous year total assets	1 IF CFO > ROA ELSE 0
F_ΔLEVER	Leverage, liquidity, and source of funds	Changes in the company's long term debt levels	1 IF ΔLEVER < 0 ELSE 0
F_ΔLIQUID		Change in the company's current ratio between the current and prior year	1 IF ΔLIQUID > 0 ELSE 0
EQ_OFFER		Captures whether a company has issued equity in the year preceding portfolio formation	1 IF EQ_OFFER < 0 ELSE 0
F_ΔMARGIN	Operating efficiency	ΔMARGIN as the company's current gross margin ratio (gross margin divided by total sales) less the prior year's gross margin ratio	1 IF ΔMARGIN > 0 ELSE 0
F_ΔTURN		The company's current year asset turnover ratio (total sales scaled by beginning of the year total assets) less the prior year's asset turnover ratio	1 IF ΔTURN > 0 ELSE 0

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

Scores range from 0 (poor value/quality stock) to 9 (very good value/quality stock) as formula (4) shows. Piotroski has shown that it is possible by only using fundamental analysis (that is using historical financial ratios and performances), to separate "winners" which have potential to generate high expected returns, from "losers" which are expected to generate low or negative returns. His experiment results showed that the average returns of an investment strategy in stocks with a high book-to-market ratio can be considerably increased by at least 7.5% annually by selecting stocks among those with high book-to-market ratio. Among other

findings, Piotroski has shown that the success of his strategy lies in the ability to predict future company performance based on past fundamentals and which the market cannot anticipate.

$$\begin{aligned} F_SCORE = & F_ROA + F_ΔROA + F_CFO + F_ACCRUAL \\ & + F_ΔLEVER + F_ΔLIQUID + EQ_OFFER \\ & + F_ΔMARGIN + F_ΔTURN \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

So far, the relevance of companies' fundamentals to serve as a criterion for portfolio selection is more than evident. Nowadays, the growing importance of machine learning tools in all areas has motivated several attempts to use financial indicators to systemize investment decisions. Most of the time, many related works of Kaczmarek & Perez (2021), El Karoui, Ban, & Lim (2018), etc. tend to approach the subject from the angle of machine learning, starting from a predictive analysis using the company's fundamentals and then to select the stocks with the best-predicted performances. Nevertheless, this paper's angle is the value investing paradigm: how can value investing be modeled and systematically applied for effective portfolio selection? To answer this question, the value investor is defined through a conceptual modelization of his behavior — as one who makes portfolio selection based on his expectations of the future returns of stocks, through the experience and knowledge acquired by learning and understanding the past and current financial fundamentals. Finally, this paper shows how a particular algorithm meets the requirements for its implementation.

2. Background

It is common knowledge that when faced with multiple choices of stocks in general, the decision maker hereafter referred to as the investor, acts according to his preferences and budget. This idea is already conveyed by consumer theory in microeconomics, which tries to solve the same problem in the context of the consumer with respect to goods and services. Markowitz (1952) defined portfolio selection problem in two stages, the first deals with investor observation, experience and belief about the future of stocks. The second stage tackle the choice among the available stocks. Markowitz then focus on the second stage though what is now known as the Modern Portfolio Theory. It approaches the issue of stock allocation from the same angle where investor preferences are described by the first two moments (mean and variance) of returns. Even in more traditional approaches such as value investing, to detect undervalued stocks, investors conduct analysis based on the fundamentals of the underlying company (underlying here emphasize the fact that behind every stock in the market there is a real company that is the issuer). As paradigm value investing deals more with the first stage of

the process of selecting a portfolio as stated by Markowitz. Observation, experience and belief about the future of stocks is a knowledge that helps value investor to select one or another stock. This common knowledge is therefore a hypothetical result of rational reasoning which consisting of decisions on the basis of available information, consistent with Rational Choice Theory, which “states that individuals rely on rational calculations to make rational choices that result in outcomes aligned with their own best interests”³. This observation is more evident from the perspective of an experienced investor, who has the expertise to judge the "quality" of a stock; judgment not based on an affinity for the stock but in relation to the investor's assessable preferences toward a stock.

2.1. Conceptual model of value investor behavior

Through Graham's work (1949), one can rationalize the behavior of a value investor as Markowitz did in the general framework of an investor. It is therefore considered that for a basket of n given stocks, an investor is able to enumerate a finite number p of variables or characteristics that describe each one of them and that he can understand, interpret and infer the effect, based on his experiences and uses in the stock's selection process. Before further discussion, it is important to consider and define concepts and objects to be used:

- S_i , represents a stock i described by a set of p dynamic (that is time dependent) properties or variables hereafter referred to as features that define S_i .
- Y_i , a target measure or metric drawn directly or indirectly after transformation from performance variables of S_i . For example, Annualized Mean Return or Sharpe ratio, etc.
- X_i , is the matrix representing the set of features, for example, Return On Asset or Quick Ratio, etc. These features are properties, characteristics or descriptors of S_i

The conceptual investor is by reasoning a value investor who is considered to make use of a traditional investment approach that is fundamental analysis:

- In that he seeks to buy undervalued stocks to sell them at higher price later when the market has corrected their price,

³ Definition from [Investopedia](#)

- But its objective is not to determine the intrinsic value of the underlying company in order to compare it to the market price but to identify this by using the features which can actually characterize that state. Identifying and buying a stock at low price (meaning undervalued) and selling it at a higher price later, is equivalent to anticipating stock with an expected return, which is strictly greater than 0. The conceptual investor will therefore identify these factors or descriptors which affect the objective in terms of expected average return of the investor.
- The connection that the investor makes between these factors/features and his objectives is not only explanatory, it is also inferential; that is by its experience or empirical study, the conceptual investor is capable of naming precisely, with a certain level of confidence, the direction of the relation between a specific factor and his objective:

$$Y = f(X) + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

and he has a predictive view also, in that the investor's goal is to predict the output value Y for new given observations of X . This definition also includes temporal forecasting, where observations until period t are used to forecast future values of Y at period $t + 1$:

$$Y_{(t+1)} = f(X_{(t)}) + \epsilon \quad (6)$$

- Between two stocks S_i and S_j , he is able to choose the best one considering the first three principles by maximizing his utility function that is Y . That is, when given for S_i and S_j respectively x_{it} and x_{jt} their feature's x values at period t to choose, the conceptual investor is able to say whether S_i or S_j is dominant or if there is no significant difference between S_i and S_j .
- And finally, the conceptual investor follows a top-down approach while analyzing stocks. It means, given a set of stocks, he always uses comprehensive factors or variables or characteristics that are relevant to him to decide which stocks are the best regarding one factor. He applies reclusively this procedure until he has exhausted the factors and has a finite subset of stocks that qualified.

As can be noticed in this exposition, the conceptual investor follows a heuristic procedure as a well-informed investor would have done by choosing among several available stocks that are adequate according to his experience and belief. The model that emerges from this investor

behavior already gives indications of the tools that can allow the implementation of the conceptual investor.

2.2. The experience or knowledge acquisition

In the literature on empirical finance, works such as (Fama & French, 1988), (Balvers, Cosimano, & McDonald, 1990), (Piotroski, 2000), (Lewellen, 2004) etc. shed the light on several fundamentals or financial indicators that are considered to be significant in terms of predicting stocks future returns. Among these fundamentals are recurrent ones like the Book-to-market ratio, the Return On Equity, the Return On Asset, etc. which have been defined earlier in this paper. More over Often value investors have a precise list of financial indicators and rules which help them decide whether or not to buy a stock and indicate if the stock is likely to generate an excess return or not. Among practitioners, each investor can explain and justify his/her choice of financial indicators and his/her own set of rules. However, in reality, it is well known that all of these are rules of thumb in the sense that they are heuristic recommendations providing practical guidelines resulting from experience rather than rigorous scientific conclusions. For example, investors use the Price to Earnings ratio (Price/Earnings or P/E) to determine whether or not a stock price is undervalued. If the P/E is low, it might show that the stock is undervalued. How does one decide it is low? Often some investors compare individual stock P/E with their industry average P/E, some with the whole market like the average P/E of S&P 500. Generally, when these sets of indicators and rules sound plausible, are reasonable, and are the result of good judgment, it is enough for them to be accepted as knowledge within the field.

With the definition of the conceptual investor, there should be a way to replicate these abilities of choosing the desired financial indicators and also extracting rules as true investors would, heuristically by learning through experience. As outlined in the previous section, a conceptual investor is designed as an agent mimicking human value investor reasoning. It should by construction, be able to reproduce the similar behavior that is to identify the main factors/variables, to induce meaningful rules and to deduce the best set of stocks which is the selected portfolio. By this attempt our model bridges into Artificial Intelligence (AI). Concerning AI, Wu (1993) states that Machine Learning (ML) is a major core in AI field, tackling how machines can acquire the knowledge that might enable them to perform some tasks that usually require human expertise (without ignoring the fact that there is knowledge

bottleneck problem when it comes to transfer from human to knowledge-based systems, knowledge as A Feigenbaum (1981) pointed out).

In ML, there are different types of algorithms, including supervised learning algorithms, which deal with problems that are formulated as (5) and (6). Quinlan (1988) has previously pointed out that learning from examples is the best way to avoid the knowledge bottleneck problem, that is to induce rules from a set of available. This is the core logic behind supervised learning – the inductive learning. From the angle of inductive learning, there is a given set of sample inputs X and sample output Y and the problem is to learn and estimate the function f such that $f(X) = Y$. More specifically, the problem is the ability to generalize from the samples (X, Y) and the mapping f also known as learner or classifier or even more precisely inducer, to be useful to predict or estimate the output for new samples later.

Among many supervised learning algorithms, the ones which interest this research paper are the decision trees, because they are able not only to induce rules, but also to produce a selection of relevant financial indicators making it possible to predict or estimate output for new future samples based on unlabeled sample input.

2.3. Decision tree induction and portfolio prediction

Decision tree is a very simple algorithm able to handle multiple variable analysis. As such one may assume it is just another ML algorithm, but the appeal of decision trees is found in their ease of use, understanding (being a white box model able to read and explain easily in contrast with black box models such as Neural Network) and of course their robustness while handling variables with different scales and missing data. Decision trees in addition to allowing for prediction, explanatory and descriptive analyses as many others algorithms, have a unique manner of doing so by turning raw data into an increased and applicable knowledge for business and research issues and enable us to deploy that knowledge in a simple but powerful set of human-readable rules (DeVille, 2006). Ultimately, what makes decision trees an adequate strategy to predict portfolios is that they discover knowledge by learning strong relationships between input samples and output samples by grouping observations into smaller, homogeneous sets.

2.3.1. Decision tree construction

A decision tree is a non-parametric ML algorithm, meaning it makes no prior hypothesis or assumptions regarding the type of probability distribution of data and according to type

categorical/numeric continuous of the output samples (referred to as target variable as fits in ML) they are known as classification/regression tree. In fact, the most popular algorithm used in many software programs to grow decision trees, is the CART Algorithm (Classification And Regression Trees) developed by Breiman, Friedman, Olshen, & Stone (1984), using "greedy" recursive partitioning approaches to minimize prediction error. The principle of construction of a Decision tree (in this paper only CART algorithm is used) is as follows:

- It starts from a root made up of the total sample's data (specifically the training data composed of all features and target variables) of the n observations, that is the root node, then a splitting variable X_j is chosen according to a specific criterion, to divide or partition or segment in two sub-populations. Thus, there are two branches each having its sub-population or partition as its termination. These new termination nodes are called internal nodes because they will serve as the new point of decision in the next step.
- For each of these new internal nodes another splitting variable is chosen that optimizes the previous chosen criterion to grow new branches with their nodes etc. this procedure is recursively repeated until either a predefined stopping condition is validated or the available variables are exhausted. Thus, sub-populations, called leaf or terminal nodes, are obtained at the terminal branches.

This raises the question of how to choose the splitting variable at each decision node. To answer this, given N_m , the number of observations in the data D_m at a partitioning node m . θ_m , a candidate splitting pair (x_j, s_m) where x_j is a candidate variable with j ranging from $1, \dots, p$ and s_m the point or partitioning threshold of D_m into $D_m^{left}(\theta)$ and $D_m^{right}(\theta)$, respectively the sub-populations to the left and to the right of the decision node such that:

$$D_m^{left}(\theta) = \{(x, y) \mid x_j \leq s_m\}$$

$$D_m^{right}(\theta) = \{(x, y) \mid x_j > s_m\}$$
(7)

and also define $H(D)$, a hypothesis function of impurity measurement or a cost function (degree of dissimilarity or degree of entropy), θ^* , the best splitting pair (x_j, s_m) is then chosen such that it minimizes the following quantities:

$$\frac{N_m^{left}}{N_m} H(D_m^{left}(\theta)) + \frac{N_m^{right}}{N_m} H(D_m^{right}(\theta))$$
(8)

which is the weighted mean of the cost function of the two sub-populations. This optimization search is done iteratively at a node m , on all possible candidates splitting pairs (x_j, s_m) , in order

to find one which minimizes this. Likewise, recursively, the same procedure is applied to each new splitting node $D_m^{left}(\theta^*)$ and $D_m^{right}(\theta^*)$ until N_m is equal to 1 or less than a fixed minimum or a certain stop condition is validated. Depending on the type of decision tree, classification or regression tree, different kinds of functions can be distinguished which can be a measure of impurity and are presented in table (Table 2). Another famous decision trees strategy is ID3 (Iterative Dichotomize3) developed by (Quinlan, 1986), using the entropy measure to calculate the information gain after each partitioning within the framework of a classification. This algorithm has been improved to obtain the C4.5 (Quinlan, 1993) algorithm which takes into account in particular numeric variables and also produces decision rules. The latest version of this algorithm which is called C5.0 is exceptionally more precise and less greedy in memory. The CART algorithm proposed by Breiman, Friedman, Olshen, & Stone (1984) only differs in its capacity to treat regression cases as mentioned above and uses the Gini index to calculate the information gain.

Table 2 : Measures of impurity

Impurity functions	Decision Tree Type	Formula
Gini Index	Classification	$H(D_m) = \sum_k f_{mk} (1 - f_{mk})$
Entropy		$H(D_m) = - \sum_k f_{mk} \log_2 f_{mk}$
Mean Squared Error	Regression	$\bar{y}_m = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{y \in D_m} y$ $\bar{y}_m = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{y \in D_m} (y - \bar{y}_m)^2$
Mean Absolute Error		$median(y)_m = median(y),$ $y \in D_m$ $H(D_m) = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{y \in D_m} y - median(y)_m $

(Source: from [Scikit-Learn](#) documentation)

2.3.2. Portfolio generation and prediction

From the Decision Trees learning or growing, several advantages emerge:

- An implicit **selection of variables** algorithm: Given the colossal number of metrics and ratios, the diversity of sources of variables that can characterize a stock or a company, decision trees are the ideal tool because they are able to deal with a large number of variables while choosing only those which are important according to the cost function. This characteristic of decision trees makes them particularly interesting, because, in practice, investment in stock has a well-defined preferential set of stock selection criteria or variables.
- An algorithm to measure the **importance of variables**: In addition to being able to sort the variables, it is also possible to obtain a measure of the importance of each variable, thus giving the possibility of judging the significance of 'one variable relative to another in partitioning.
- A **predictive** algorithm: Being a supervised ML method, decision trees allow for predictions after learning from a training sample. It is moreover this functionality that allows portfolio generation in the model under development.
- A **stratification and segmentation** algorithm: It is possible to segment the total population into sub-populations or partitions which share similar characteristics with respect to the variable to be predicted and this by stratum, that is in a hierarchical manner. This is a very beneficial property, especially for an investor in value who can easily identify individuals (companies) belonging to homogeneous structures.
- An **interpretable** algorithm: Decision trees are very easy to understand because they are not only possible to deduce decision rules but also a readable directional graph.

In addition to these abilities, in this paper, at the terminal branches, the obtained pure sub populations or homogeneous sets with respect to the features or variables (X) and the variable to be predicted (Y), are seen as portfolios. The agglomerate capacity of the decision trees that is to group observations by splitting the total data set of observations through the recursive procedure that is described in the previous section, very similar to stock screening, yet better because the sub-sets inductively generate portfolios, which are also represented by the leaves, the partitions or sub-populations at the terminal branches:

- Learning or inductive phase: Consists of learning the relationship between the set of features $X_{(t-1)}$ and Y_t . Where $X_{(t-1)}$ contains features (financials indicators) in period $(t - 1)$ that explain the performances Y_t in period t . In this sense, that same assumption which an investor makes by buying and holding a stock based on what he knows until the point of decision, in the expectation of positive or excess returns in the future, holds. In ML, this process builds a learner from decision tree algorithm based on the following model:

$$Y_{(t)} = f(X_{(t-1)}) \quad (9)$$

Through this phase, the conceptual investor acquires the experience and knowledge, because of the special ability of decision trees. Rules will be inferred in order to be generalized according to the strength of the relationship between $X_{(t-1)}$ and Y_t .

- Portfolios generation phase: A portfolio is a set of securities to which are associated proportions that represent their individual share in an investment of a monetary unit. A portfolio can therefore be represented as a set of proportions $w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_i, \dots, w_n$ given a universe of n securities, which respect the budget constraint:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_{(i)} = 1 \quad (10)$$

From previously generated rules, it is possible to predict with a new features data set $X_{(t)}$, but in this case the predicted groups are of interest. These new groups are homogeneous sets of observations, sharing the common characteristics.

- Selection and/or allocation phase: the most obvious and basic of the strategies, is quite simply to choose the group which generates the best performance $U(Y)$ where U is a utility function which aggregates and makes it possible to compare the groups or portfolios using weights which are equal or proportional to market capitalization. it can in particular be indicators of central tendency an optimization algorithm with constraint to define the weights directly like the Maximizing Sharpe Ratio.

3. Data and Experiments Design

The stocks used for this paper are the members of Standard & Poor's 500 index (S&P 500) distributed as shown in the table (Table 3). For each of the stocks the data set includes historical

price and fundamental data such as financial indicators or ratios website, which are the prices obtained from Yahoo Finance and contains daily closing prices of each stock from January 1, 2008 to December 31, 2020 and for fundamentals from MorningStar. Ten years of 59 distinct historical fundamentals from 2011 to 2020, freely available to public access online.

Table 3 : Collected data from 2011 to 2019.

Year	Observations	Number of features/variables
2011-12-31	460	59
2012-12-31	466	59
2013-12-31	476	59
2014-12-31	484	59
2015-12-31	489	59
2016-12-31	492	59
2017-12-31	492	59
2018-12-31	494	59
2019-12-31	494	59
2020-12-31	494	59

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

Each year between 2011 and 2020, backtesting is run for one year (t) by training a Regression Tree using fundamentals of year ($t-2$) as features data and mean return at end of ($t-1$) as target variable or dependent variable. Then fundamentals at the end of year ($t-1$) are used to predict many candidate portfolios (which are leaves). The one with the maximum portfolio mean return (as utility function) at the end of year ($t-1$) is selected as the optimal for

investment. Backtesting designed here is based on buy-and-hold strategy which implies no re-balancing. For comparison, these strategies are run alongside:

- Firstly, Equal-Weighted Predicted Portfolio (E-WPP), to equally weight the composition of the predicted and selected leaves as one portfolio meaning all sample stocks found in the leaves have the same weight.
- Secondly, another strategy labeled as Equal-Weighted Portfolio (E-WP), is to put in each stock the same weight so it be can possible to compare between applying naively the same weight on all listed stocks versus on a predicted portfolio.
- Standard & Poor's 500 index (S&P 500 (^GSPC)) was used as market proxy or bench mark since all stocks in the data are listed in this well-known index.

4. Results

The prediction algorithm used was the **DecisionTreeRegressor** model offered by **Scikit Learn**, which uses the previously mentioned CART strategy. The experiment proved to be compelling over the 8 periods especially considering the significant level of R-Squared scores presented in table (Table 4), calculated based on a training dataset:

Table 4 : Training R-Squared scores.

Year	R-Squared
2012-12-31	73.55%
2013-12-31	79.30%
2014-12-31	77.00%
2015-12-31	73.26%
2016-12-31	71.15%
2017-12-31	74.36%
2018-12-31	75.73%
2019-12-31	66.21%

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

As the table (Table 5) shows in 2020, despite the fact that that 2020 was very difficult for the global economy and market in the beginning due to COVID19, the Equal-Weighted Predicted Portfolio yielded a total return of 218% versus 14% and 15% respectively for Equal-Weighted Portfolio and S&P 500 (^GSPC). This is very extreme result considering that the related volatility is at 62% in 2020 which is almost twice the average volatility of 33% for the entire backtesting period. The rest of the results can be seen in the performance summary table with the global annual mean return of 69.9% for Equal-Weighted Predicted Portfolio (E-WPP) compared to only 18.4% for (E-WPP) and 13.1% S&P 500 (^ GSPC). Consequently, on the other hand, the volatility is also proportional and aligned with the level of total return.

Table 5 : Buy-and-Hold Equal-Weighted Predicted Portfolio (E-WPP) strategy versus Equal-Weighted Portfolio (E-WP) and S&P 500, performances summary.

Designation	Year	Total Return	Max. Drawdown	Sharpe Ratio	Mean Return	Volatility
E-WPP	2013	0.37	-0.13	1.46	0.35	0.24
E-WP		0.37	-0.06	2.74	0.33	0.12
S&P 500		0.26	-0.06	2.23	0.24	0.11
E-WPP	2014	0.58	-0.29	1.39	0.54	0.39
E-WP		0.20	-0.08	1.60	0.19	0.12
S&P 500		0.12	-0.07	1.09	0.12	0.11
E-WPP	2015	0.18	-0.13	0.85	0.20	0.23
E-WP		0.04	-0.11	0.34	0.05	0.15
S&P 500		-0.01	-0.12	0.03	0.01	0.16
E-WPP	2016	0.32	-0.23	0.96	0.35	0.36
E-WP		0.19	-0.10	1.26	0.18	0.14

S&P 500		0.11	-0.09	0.89	0.12	0.13
E-WPP	2017	0.21	-0.05	1.56	0.20	0.13
E-WP		0.24	-0.02	3.00	0.22	0.07
S&P 500		0.18	-0.03	2.59	0.17	0.07
E-WPP	2018	0.37	-0.20	1.12	0.37	0.33
E-WP		-0.05	-0.19	-0.25	-0.04	0.16
S&P 500		-0.07	-0.20	-0.34	-0.06	0.17
E-WPP	2019	1.37	-0.30	2.56	0.93	0.36
E-WP		0.33	-0.06	2.33	0.29	0.13
S&P 500		0.29	-0.07	2.09	0.26	0.12
E-WPP	2020	2.18	-0.39	2.17	1.35	0.62
E-WP		0.15	-0.38	0.57	0.20	0.36
S&P 500		0.15	-0.34	0.59	0.20	0.34
E-WPP	Mean	0.70	-0.22	1.51	0.54	0.33
E-WP		0.18	-0.13	1.45	0.18	0.16
S&P 500		0.13	-0.12	1.15	0.13	0.15

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

Although decision trees as ML algorithm are not sensitive to outliers or extreme values like some others ML algorithms (for outliers are never chosen as split point), adjusting the portfolio size (the number of stocks) for diversification purpose to avoid extreme result like in 2020 must be considered. The CART algorithm used makes it possible to control the minimum size of each group or leaf during training, but during the prediction phase this minimum is not guaranteed as the size of each predicted portfolio can be seen on graph (Figure 1)

Figure 1 : Size (number of stocks or tickers) of predicted portfolios per year.

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

To ensure a certain level of diversification in the predicted portfolio, a better solution is to merge subsequent leaves so a portfolio will not be composed of only one stock like in 2016 or three stocks in 2020. Thus, another backtesting was run with minimal sample sizes of 5 at each leaf, but also a minimum of 10 stocks predicted per year and per portfolio as the graph (Figure 2) shows below.

Figure 2 : Size of predicted portfolios per year after adjusting the portfolio size minimum to 10 stock/tickers

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

(Elton, 1977) showed empirically that increasing the number of stocks to 10 in a portfolio has a significant effect in reducing the volatility, thereby increasing diversification in a portfolio. Beyond this number, the gain in diversification is residual. As result, increasing the minimum of the portfolio size to 10 has affected positively and significantly the performances (Table 6).

Table 6 : Performances summary after adjusting the minimum portfolio size at 10 stocks.

Designation	Year	Total Re turn	Max. Draw down	Sharpe Ratio	Mean Re turn	Volatility
E-WPP	2013	0.31	-0.09	1.75	0.28	0.16
E-WP		0.37	-0.06	2.74	0.33	0.12
S&P 500		0.26	-0.06	2.23	0.24	0.11
E-WPP	2014	0.30	-0.17	1.24	0.29	0.24
E-WP		0.20	-0.08	1.60	0.19	0.12
S&P 500		0.12	-0.07	1.09	0.12	0.11
E-WPP	2015	0.08	-0.12	0.51	0.10	0.19
E-WP		0.04	-0.11	0.34	0.05	0.15
S&P 500		-0.01	-0.12	0.03	0.01	0.16
E-WPP	2016	0.16	-0.16	0.85	0.16	0.19
E-WP		0.19	-0.10	1.26	0.18	0.14
S&P 500		0.11	-0.09	0.89	0.12	0.13
E-WPP	2017	0.21	-0.05	1.56	0.20	0.13
E-WP		0.24	-0.02	3.00	0.22	0.07
S&P 500		0.18	-0.03	2.59	0.17	0.07
E-WPP	2018	0.22	-0.22	0.87	0.24	0.27
E-WP		-0.05	-0.19	-0.25	-0.04	0.16
S&P 500		-0.07	-0.20	-0.34	-0.06	0.17
E-WPP	2019	0.91	-0.20	2.82	0.68	0.24
E-WP		0.33	-0.06	2.33	0.29	0.13

S&P 500		0.29	-0.07	2.09	0.26	0.12
E-WPP	2020	0.74	-0.40	1.46	0.66	0.45
E-WP		0.15	-0.38	0.57	0.20	0.36
S&P 500		0.15	-0.34	0.59	0.20	0.34
E-WPP	Mean	0.37	-0.18	1.38	0.33	0.23
E-WP		0.18	-0.13	1.45	0.18	0.16
S&P 500		0.13	-0.12	1.15	0.13	0.15

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

As previously mentioned, decision trees as a ML algorithm make it possible to classify features by importance as shown in the table (Table 7):

Table 7 : Top important features in 2020.

Features	Importance Measure
Revenue	0.1178
Operating Income (3 year average)	0.1034
Free Cash flow	0.0847
Quick_ratio	0.0730
Cap Spending	0.0582
Payables period	0.0579
Net Income (5 year_average)	0.0463
Free Cash Flow Net Income	0.0387
Financial leverage (Average)	0.0323

(Source: Authors own elaboration)

A confirmation of the ratios used in the Piotroski F-Score can be read with Quick Ratio, Financial Leverage and Cap Spending as indicators of leverage, liquidity, and source of funds. Additionally, Free Cash Flow and Net Income as Profitability measure and finally for Operating efficiency, there are Payables period, Revenue and Operating Income.

5. Conclusion

The experiment shows that financial fundamentals are relevant indicators for predicting future returns on securities as documented in previous research. Moreover, the portfolio design process, using rules induced by decision trees to predict portfolio by selecting similar stocks, has been shown to be effective in the various backtesting carried out. The data suggests this approach can validly serve as an expert system for portfolio or asset management, especially when considering further work on the engineering stocks features and modifying the decision tree to be more robust in the training or learning step. A noted limitation of this approach is that it is greedy in data to be efficient.

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